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ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**

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Project LePWaR (Let's Play with Word and Read): Its Contribution to Reading Performance among Key Stage 2 Learners of Labu-Ay Elementary School

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Abstract

This study examined the efficacy of project LePWaR, a game-based reading instructional tool, in enhancing the reading performance of key stage 2 learners at Labu-ay Elementary School during the first quarter of the 2023-2024 academic year. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, the study focuses on the influence of project LePWaR on the reading fluency and vocabulary levels of a selected group of 30 learners. Furthermore, the research explores the association between the game-based reading instructional tool and the fluency and vocabulary levels of key stage 2 learners. The investigation employs pre- and post-assessment measures, incorporating the Phil-IRI assessment tool for English oral reading. Additionally, qualitative data are gathered through adapted and modified survey questionnaires and open-ended interviews to evaluate the project's impact comprehensively. Based on the findings, the intervention produced significant improvements in vocabulary ($M = 56.79$) and fluency ($M = 27.56$) post-test scores, along with a noticeable rise in standard deviation. These results suggest that learners have improved a wider range of skills, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention in promoting fluency and vocabulary acquisition. The implications of the study's findings for practice, educational policies, and future research are significant. For practice, educators can consider integrating game-based instructional tools like project LePWaR into their teaching methods, particularly for enhancing reading fluency and vocabulary among key stage 2 learners. This approach can provide engaging and effective learning experiences, catering to diverse learning styles and preferences. Moreover, educational policies could be informed by these results, potentially advocating for the integration of similar game-based interventions into curriculum frameworks or funding initiatives to support innovative teaching practices. Future research could build upon this study by delving deeper into the specific mechanisms through which game-based learning impacts reading proficiency. Investigating factors such as learner engagement, motivation, and cognitive processes during gameplay could offer valuable insights for optimizing instructional design. Additionally, exploring the long-term effects of such interventions and their sustainability over extended periods would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of their efficacy and practical implications. Integrating these implications into the abstract would enrich its relevance and inform readers about the broader significance of the study's findings.

Keywords: *project LePWaR, Phil-IRI assessment tool, key stage 2 learners, game-based reading instructional tool*

Introduction

Reading performance encompasses an individual's ability to read and understand written content, involving word recognition, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. The National Center for Education Statistics (NCES) emphasizes the importance of reading for academic and lifelong success National Center for Education Statistics (n.d.).

In the Philippines, there is a concerning low reading proficiency among intermediate learners (Philippine Department of Education, 2020). Data from the 2019 Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) and the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) highlight this issue. The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated the problem due to the shift to distance learning and limited access to reading materials. A 2021 survey by the Philippine Normal University revealed that 60% of Filipino students struggled with reading during the pandemic. Limited access to books at home was identified as a contributing factor World Health Organization (2020).

To address this issue, a game-based reading instructional tool called LePWaR (Let's Play with Word and Read) was developed. Designed for key stage 2 learners (Grades 4-6), LePWaR aims to enhance fluency and vocabulary by engaging students in interactive reading games. Inspired by the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) and anchored in educational theories such as Lev Vygotsky's social constructivist theory and B.F. Skinner's behaviorism, LePWaR integrates game elements to motivate learning.

The study conducted in Labu-ay Elementary School during the 2023–2024 school year aimed to evaluate LePWaR's effectiveness in improving key stage 2 learners' reading performance in terms of fluency and vocabulary. Preliminary findings suggest that the game-based approach could be a promising strategy to address reading challenges among intermediate learners.

The researchers believe that LePWaR could be a valuable tool for teachers and policymakers to enhance reading instruction and support struggling readers. While international studies have explored various interventions to improve reading performance, there is a gap in understanding the effectiveness of specific strategies tailored to the context of developing countries like the Philippines. Existing research may focus on interventions such as phonics-based instruction, reading comprehension strategies, or technology-based

approaches. However, there is limited exploration of how these interventions can be adapted and implemented effectively within the Philippine educational system, considering factors such as language diversity, socio-economic disparities, and infrastructure challenges. Although studies in the Philippines have investigated reading performance issues, there is a gap in research regarding the scalability and sustainability of interventions. While some studies may have demonstrated short-term improvements in reading outcomes, there is a need for longitudinal research to assess the long-term impact of interventions on reading proficiency among learners. Additionally, there is a gap in understanding how socio-cultural factors, community engagement, and policy frameworks influence the success of reading interventions in the Philippine context. The rationale behind conducting LEPWAR for Stage 2 learners is not explicitly stated in the available literature. Understanding the specific observations or baseline data that informed the decision to target this particular group of learners would provide valuable insights into the research context. Exploring factors such as baseline reading proficiency levels, identified learning needs, and curriculum alignment could help justify the selection of Stage 2 learners as the target population for the intervention. While there have been studies examining reading interventions, the uniqueness of LEPWAR lies in its game-based approach and its application within the Philippine educational context. Existing studies may have focused on traditional instructional methods or technology-based interventions without the gamified elements present in LEPWAR. Furthermore, LEPWAR may differentiate itself through its integration of culturally relevant content, interactive design features, or alignment with local curriculum standards. Understanding how LEPWAR differs from previous studies in terms of design, implementation strategies, and anticipated outcomes can provide insights into its potential effectiveness and contribution to the field of reading instruction.

Research Questions

This study investigated the effectiveness of project LePWaR as a game-based reading instructional tool on the reading performance of key stage 2 learners in Labu-ay Elementary School during the first quarter of the academic year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study opted to answer the following questions:

1. How did the reading skills of key stage 2 students at Labu-ay Elementary School change before and after using the LePWaR project, a game-based tool, for fluency and vocabulary?
2. What is the level of experience of the key stage 2 learners with project LePWaR?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners and their level of experience and post-test scores of fluency and vocabulary?
4. Is there a significant relationship in the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners between their pre-test and post-test scores?
5. What modification can be proposed to improve the intervention plan?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a quasi-experimental research design to evaluate the effectiveness of the researcher's game-based reading instructional tool, LePWaR, on improving the reading fluency and vocabulary of key stage 2 learners during remediation classes. The study also employed the triangulation method through surveys and interviews.

A quasi-experimental design resembles an experimental design but lacks random assignment of participants to experimental and control groups. Instead, pre-existing groups or conditions are compared to assess the effects of an intervention. Quasi-experimental designs are often used when randomization is impractical or unethical. According to Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018), quasi-experimental designs allow researchers to study naturally occurring groups or conditions and are useful for evaluating interventions in real-world settings.

In the context of the study, a quasi-experimental design was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to assess the impact of the LePWaR reading instructional tool on key stage 2 learners' reading fluency and vocabulary in a practical educational setting. Given the constraints of conducting randomized controlled trials in school environments, a quasi-experimental design allowed for the comparison of pre-existing groups (i.e., learners receiving remediation classes) before and after the intervention. This design facilitated the evaluation of changes in reading performance attributable to the LePWaR intervention while accounting for contextual factors and practical considerations inherent in educational research.

To ensure data accuracy, the Phil-IRI assessment tool was employed for both pre-test and post-test evaluations of English oral reading. This systematic method aimed to validate the efficacy of the instructional tool and determine the specific impact of LePWaR on reading skills enhancement.

The study also employed purposive sampling, for the qualitative research technique, to select a specific group of participants from the total population. This sampling method ensured that eligible participants were chosen based on the study's purpose and objectives

Respondents

The study focused on thirty frustrated readers from key stage 2 at Labu-ay Elementary School for the academic year 2023-2024, identified based on the Phil-IRI assessment. The inclusion criteria for teacher-participants in this study were carefully defined to ensure

that they met specific qualifications and characteristics necessary for the successful implementation of the LePWaR reading instructional tool. Teacher-participants were selected based on the following criteria:

Educational Background: Teachers were required to possess a minimum qualification of a bachelor's degree in education or a related field, with specialization or experience in teaching language arts or literacy instruction.

Teaching Experience: Teacher-participants were required to have a minimum of two years of teaching experience in elementary education, particularly in delivering reading instruction to key stage 2 learners.

Interest and Willingness: Teachers who expressed genuine interest and willingness to participate in the study and incorporate the LePWaR reading instructional tool into their remediation classes were included.

Availability: Teacher-participants needed to be available to attend training sessions on how to effectively use the LePWaR tool and to implement it during remediation classes throughout the duration of the study.

Instruments

The Phil-IRI English assessment tool, aligned with D.O. 14, s. 2018, was used to evaluate the reading performance of the respondents. Four sets of reading materials from Phil-IRI were used for pre-test and post-test assessments. Comprehensive interview questions and two distinct survey questionnaires were also administered to gather data from educators and key stage 2 learners. A five-point Likert scale was used to rate indicators, with validation conducted through consultations with the research adviser.

To establish further validity of the research tools used, validation scores were developed based on established criteria for categorizing reading proficiency levels. The validation scores for both the independent and instructional levels were aligned with predetermined benchmarks. These scores were as follows:

Independent Level: Scores falling between 80 and 100 were categorized as independent. This range indicates that learners have demonstrated a high level of proficiency and autonomy in reading comprehension and fluency.

Instructional Level: Scores ranging from 59 to 79 were classified as instructional. Learners within this range have shown competency in reading but may benefit from some level of guidance and instruction to fully comprehend more complex texts or vocabulary.

Frustration Level: Scores below 58% were considered to be in the frustration level. Learners in this category may struggle significantly with the text, experiencing difficulty comprehending or engaging with the material.

The interpretation of the validation scores is as follows:

Independent Level (Fluency): Scores ranging from 97 to 100 indicate that learners are reading fluently and confidently, demonstrating a mastery of the text. This level suggests that learners can easily decode words and comprehend passages without significant difficulty.

Instructional Level (Fluency): Scores falling between 90 and 96 suggest that learners are reading at an instructional level. While they demonstrate fluency and comprehension, they may encounter some challenges with more complex vocabulary or sentence structures.

Frustration Level (Fluency): Scores below 89% indicate that learners are experiencing frustration in reading fluency. They may struggle with decoding words, maintaining comprehension, or engaging with the text effectively.

Procedure

The Phil-IRI pre-test was administered at the start of the school year to determine reading levels. Identified frustrated readers then participated in the LePWaR game-based reading instructional tool sessions for 30 minutes daily over one week. Pre-tests and post-tests were conducted using the same reading materials to assess improvements in fluency and vocabulary. Adapted survey questionnaires and interview questions were provided to the respondents and teachers post-intervention for further insights

Data Analysis

The study employed mean, standard deviation, and Pearson product-moment correlation to analyze the data. These tools were used to describe fluency and vocabulary levels, determine the correlation between pre-test and post-test scores, and assess the level of experience of the key stage 2 learners.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring no psychological harm and maintaining data confidentiality. The researchers committed to using the data responsibly without causing harm to the participants or the school.

Ethical considerations are paramount in any research endeavor, particularly when involving human participants, as they ensure the protection of individuals' rights, well-being, and confidentiality. In the context of the present study evaluating the efficacy of the LePWaR game-based reading instructional tool, several ethical considerations were carefully addressed to uphold the integrity and validity of the research while safeguarding the rights and welfare of all involved parties.

First and foremost, informed consent was obtained from all participants, including both learners and teacher-participants, prior to their involvement in the study. This ensured that individuals were fully aware of the nature of their participation, the objectives of the research, any potential risks or benefits, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions. In the case of minors, informed consent was also obtained from their legal guardians to ensure that they were fully informed and supportive of their child's participation.

Additionally, measures were implemented to protect the confidentiality and privacy of participants' personal information. Data collected from surveys, interviews, and assessments were anonymized and aggregated to prevent the identification of individual participants. Confidentiality agreements were also established with all involved parties, including researchers, teachers, and school administrators, to ensure that sensitive information remained protected and used solely for research purposes.

Furthermore, the research protocol adhered to ethical guidelines outlined by relevant institutional review boards (IRBs) or ethics committees. These guidelines ensure that research involving human participants complies with established ethical principles, including beneficence, nonmaleficence, justice, and respect for autonomy. By adhering to these ethical principles, the study prioritized the well-being and rights of participants while striving to generate meaningful and valuable insights into effective reading instruction.

Moreover, equitable access to educational resources and opportunities was promoted throughout the study, particularly considering the potential disparities in access to technology or educational support among participants. Efforts were made to ensure that the LePWaR intervention was accessible to all learners, regardless of socioeconomic status, geographic location, or other demographic factors. This commitment to equity helped mitigate potential biases and ensured that the research findings were representative of diverse learner populations.

Lastly, throughout the research process, ongoing monitoring and evaluation were conducted to assess the impact of the intervention on participants and to identify any unforeseen ethical concerns or issues that may have arisen. Researchers remained vigilant in addressing any emerging ethical dilemmas promptly and transparently, prioritizing the welfare and rights of participants above all else.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussions of the study, including the analysis and interpretation.

Problem 1. What is the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners in Labu-ay Elementary School before and after implementing project LePWaR as a game-based reading instructional tool in terms of fluency and vocabulary?

Table 1. Mean Level of Respondents' Vocabulary Levels and Fluency Level in Pre-test and Post-test

	N=30		Pre-test		Post-test	
Vocabulary	13.43	Frustration	70.22	Independent		
Fluency	5.16	Frustration	32.720	Frustration		

Legend for Vocabulary: Independent- 80-100; Instructional- 59-79; 58% below - Frustration
Legend for Fluency: Independent- 97-100; Instructional- 90-96; 89% below - Frustration

It can be seen that the post-test scores for vocabulary had accelerated from a frustration level to an independent level. It is noticeable that after the intervention, their vocabulary level improved in favor of the post-test scores in vocabulary. It is very interesting to note that the post-test mean score had increased. It is important to note that, although the fluency of the respondents is still at the frustration level their score has significantly increased by 27.56.

This implies that the intervention implemented in the study significantly improved their fluency and vocabulary. The result of this fluency remaining at frustration level could suggest a potential correlation between the intervention and the enhancement of vocabulary skills among learners. According to Saleh, A., and Althaqafi, A. S. A., in their study "The Effect of Using Educational Games as a Tool in Teaching English Vocabulary to Arab Young Children: A Quasi-Experimental Study in a Kindergarten School in Saudi Arabia," they found that using educational games to teach vocabulary had many positive effects on the participants, as it has been found that games can entertain, teach, motivate, and enhance young learners' vocabulary.

In an interview conducted with the teacher regarding their observation of their learners improvement upon playing project LePWaR the teacher said:

Teachers 1, 2, 3 and 4: "This project LePWaR improves their vocabulary, fluency as well as word recognition and speed in reading as learners set familiar with the sight words and memorize the spelling of words."

Problem 2. What is the level of experience of the key stage 2 learners with project LePWaR?

As revealed, learners rated "very true to me" in all the indicators of their experiences with the intervention. Following positive experiences with the project LePWaR intervention, learners reported an overall mean score of 1.19, indicating high satisfaction and effectiveness with the intervention.

This implies a strong positive reception among learners for the project LePWaR intervention, as evidenced by their unanimous 'very

true to me' ratings across all indicators. The resulting overall mean score of 1.19 indicates a highly favorable experience. This aligns with prior research by Ali Derakhshan and Elham Davoodi Khatir, "The Effects of Using Games on English Vocabulary Learning," which revealed that games are beneficial in vocabulary learning because they enhance learners' ability to memorize words, encourage learners' interaction, improve their communicative skills, and enhance learners' motivation.

Table 2. *Presentation of the Level of Experience of the Learners with the Intervention*

Statements about Experiences	Experiences of key stage 2 learners during the conduct of the project LePWaR				
	X	SD	Description	Interpretation	
1. It was easy to use LePWaR as a game-based reading instructional tool.	1.03	.18	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
2. I found using LePWaR fun.	1.00	.00	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
3. Using LePWaR kept me motivated to interact with other learners and do reading.	1.13	.345	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
4. The use of LePWaR helped me learn new vocabulary.	1.26	.784	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
5. I prefer the use of games in learning to read instead of paper and pen alone.	1.60	1.40	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
6. The use of LePWaR helped me to improve my reading skills.	1.03	.18	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
7. LePWaR encouraged me improve my fluency in reading.	1.06	.25	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
8. LePWaR encouraged me to concentrate in reading.	1.10	.30	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
9. LePWaR has reinforced my English language understanding.	1.13	.57	Strongly Agree	Very True to me	
	Mean	1.15	.19	Strongly Agree	Very True to me

Legend for: Very untrue to me 4.21-5.00; Untrue to me 4.41-4.20; Neutral 2.61-3.40; True to me 1.81-2.60; Very true to me 1.00-1.80

As revealed, learners rated "very true to me" in all the indicators of their experiences with the intervention. Following positive experiences with the project LePWaR intervention, learners reported an overall mean score of 1.19, indicating high satisfaction and effectiveness with the intervention.

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In an interview conducted with the teacher regarding their observation to their learners improvement upon playing project LePWaR the teacher said:

Teacher 1 and 3: "Project LePWaR contribute to the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners in terms of their fluency and vocabulary by memorizing or familiarization. And they enjoy reading while playing "Making reading fun". Enjoying while learning."

In an interview conducted among the respondents regarding their experience upon playing project LePWaR the respondents said:

Teacher 2 and 4: "I enjoy playing the game because there's a reward, so I practice reading at home."

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners and their level of experience and post-test scores of fluency and vocabulary?

Table 3. *Correlation Analysis of the Level of Experience and Post-test Scores*

	Dependent Variable:		
	R-value	P-value	Remarks
Vocabulary	0.485	0.007*	Significant
Fluency	.175	.356	Not Significant

Legend: Very Weak-0.0-0.20; Weak-0.21-0.40; Moderate-0.41-0.60; Strong-0.61-0.80;

Very Strong-0.81-1.00

* Significant at 0.05 level

As gleaned from the table above, the level of experiences and post-test scores for vocabulary have a p-value less than 0.05, which is below the significant level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of experiences and post-test scores of the vocabulary skills was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the level of experience and the post-test scores of the vocabulary skills of the learners. This means that their experiences with the intervention are connected to their vocabulary post-test scores.

However, the level of experiences and the fluency post-test scores have a p-value greater than 0.05 which is below the significant level

at 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of experiences and the post-test scores for fluency is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the level of experience and post-test scores for fluency among the learners. This means that their experiences with the intervention do not affect their fluency scores.

This implies that the learners' experiences with the intervention are linked to their vocabulary post-test scores, as evidenced by the rejection of the null hypothesis for vocabulary skills. However, there's no substantial connection found between their experiences and the fluency post-test scores, indicating that the intervention did not significantly impact their fluency scores. According to O'Connor et al. (2007; Torgesen & Hudson (2006). Reading fluency intervention programs have lower levels of improvement compared to other reading programs, such as phonemic awareness and decoding. However, based on the theory of automaticity, Samuels introduced the method of repeated reading as a good way to support reading fluency.

In an interview conducted among the respondents regarding their experience upon playing project LePWaR the respondents said:

Teacher 1 and 2: *"I really improved in my reading after playing LepWaR."*

Teacher 3 and 4: *"It helped, I can read now, a little faster and I learned some new words."*

Problem 4. Is there a significant difference and relationship in the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners between their pre-test and post-test scores?

Table 4. Correlation Analysis of Pre-test and Post-test Scores

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable:		
	Pre-test	Post-test	
	R-value	P-value	Remarks
Vocabulary	0.383	0.029*	Significant
Fluency	.460	.010*	Significant

Legend: Very Weak-0.0-0.20; Weak-0.21-0.40; Moderate-0.41-0.60; Strong-0.61-0.80; Very Strong-0.81-1.00

As gleaned from the table above, the pre-test and post-test scores have a p-value less than 0.05, which is below the significant level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the pre-test and post-test scores was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the pre-test and post-test scores of fluencies and vocabulary. Moreover, the pre-test and post-test scores were positively and weakly correlated for vocabulary, while the post-test score for fluency was positively and moderately correlated. The result implies that the intervention affects the vocabulary level and fluency of the learners. The intervention applied had a significant effect on the vocabulary and fluency of the learners.

This implies that the intervention had a significant impact on both the vocabulary and fluency of the learners, as shown by the rejected null hypothesis and the positive correlations between pre-test and post-test scores for both vocabulary and fluency.

In an interview conducted with the teacher regarding their observation to their learners improvement upon playing project LePWaR the teacher said:

Teachers 1, 3, and 4: *"The strategies and techniques of the project LePWaR can help the learners to develop their reading abilities. Because the new concept the learners encourage and challenge to learn. It also helps the learners to identify the words and its meaning. Project LePWaR is very useful and helpful with regards to the reading ability of the learners."*

Conclusions

The findings of this study underscore the profound impact of the intervention on enhancing the vocabulary levels of key stage 2 learners, despite their fluency remaining at a frustration level. This suggests that while the intervention effectively addressed certain aspects of reading proficiency, there are still opportunities for further improvement, particularly in fluency. Moreover, the overwhelmingly positive experiences reported by learners, as evidenced by their high ratings and overall mean score, highlight the effectiveness of Project LePWaR in engaging and benefiting participants. This indicates that the intervention not only yielded tangible improvements in reading skills but also fostered a supportive and enriching learning environment. Interestingly, the level of experience emerged as a significant factor influencing post-test scores for vocabulary skills, suggesting that learners with more prior experience may have exhibited greater gains in this area. However, this factor did not exert a significant influence on post-test scores for fluency, indicating that other factors may play a more prominent role in shaping fluency outcomes. The significant improvement observed in both fluency and vocabulary skills, as evidenced by the marked difference in pre-test and post-test scores, underscores the efficacy of the intervention in promoting reading proficiency among key stage 2 learners. However, the persistent frustration-level reading fluency highlights the need for targeted interventions to address this issue comprehensively. To address this challenge, it is recommended that the action plan be adjusted to include allocating one hour daily for Project LePWaR over a quarter. This extended duration of intervention may facilitate sustained progress towards achieving an independent level of fluency, thereby addressing the persistent frustration-level reading fluency observed among key stage 2 learners. While this study has yielded valuable insights into the effectiveness of Project LePWaR in enhancing reading proficiency among key stage 2 learners, further refinements and targeted interventions are necessary to address remaining challenges and ensure continued progress towards achieving optimal reading outcomes.

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are offered:

Enhance Fluency Instruction: Given the persistent frustration-level reading fluency among key stage 2 learners, it is recommended to prioritize and allocate dedicated time for fluency instruction within the curriculum. Incorporating research-based strategies and activities specifically designed to improve fluency, such as repeated reading, timed readings, and modeling fluent reading, can help learners progress towards achieving independent fluency levels.

Provide Ongoing Support and Feedback: Implement a structured support system to provide ongoing guidance and feedback to learners as they engage with the LePWaR intervention. This can include regular check-ins with teachers or mentors, individualized feedback on reading performance, and opportunities for peer collaboration and support. By fostering a supportive learning environment, learners can receive the necessary encouragement and assistance to overcome challenges and make meaningful progress in their reading skills.

Tailor Intervention to Individual Needs: Recognize the diverse learning needs and preferences of key stage 2 learners by offering personalized intervention plans. Conducting assessments to identify specific areas of strength and areas for improvement in fluency and vocabulary can inform the development of individualized learning pathways. Providing differentiated instruction and resources tailored to each learner's unique needs can maximize the effectiveness of the intervention and ensure equitable access to learning opportunities.

Integrate Multimodal Learning Approaches: Explore innovative ways to enhance the LePWaR intervention by integrating multimodal learning approaches. Incorporating audiovisual resources, interactive games, and multimedia content can cater to diverse learning styles and preferences, making the learning experience more engaging and effective. By leveraging technology and multimedia resources, learners can strengthen their reading skills in dynamic and interactive ways, leading to deeper comprehension and retention of content.

Promote Home-School Collaboration: Foster collaboration between educators, parents, and caregivers to extend the impact of the intervention beyond the classroom. Encourage parents and caregivers to actively engage in their child's reading development by providing resources, activities, and guidance for supporting reading practice at home. Establishing open communication channels between home and school can facilitate the sharing of insights, strategies, and progress updates, ensuring alignment between home and school environments in promoting reading success.

References

- Bafadal, et al. (2020). The Use of Spinning Wheel Game Media To Improve The Ability Using Modal Auxiliary Verbs For Students In Class VIII Smpn 7 Mataram Academic Year 2019-2020. *Linguistics and ELT Journal*, 7(2), 1-11. <http://tinyurl.com/3j5ef88w>
- Chen, et al. (2018). The Effect of Game-Based Learning on Key Stage 2 Learners' Reading Performance: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(4), 485–498. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/yesaz5zy>
- Department of Education (DO). (2019). Department Order No. 021, s. 2019: Policy guidelines on the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/2j6f5k3h>
- Department of Education. (2018). Department Order No. 14, s. 2018: Implementing Guidelines on the Conduct of Remedial and Advancement Classes During Summer for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/3nzuthck>
- Department of Education. (2018). Department Order No. 14, s. 2018: Policy Guidelines on the Administration of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/ymzhfjd9>
- Derakhshan, A., & El khatir, S. (2015). The Effects of Using Games on English Vocabulary Learning. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/eydtz8sa>
- Foko, T. C. (2008). Serious games as educational tools: Effects on student engagement, motivation, and learning. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 1(1), 1-14.
- Hudson, et al. (2005). Reading fluency assessment and instruction: What, why, and how? *The Reading Teacher*, 58(702-714). doi: 10.1598/RT.58.8.1
- Kamil, M. L., & Hiebert, E. H. (2005). *Teaching and learning vocabulary: Bringing research to practice*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Ladley, et al. (2013). The cognitive benefits of edutainment games: A focus on attention, memory, and executive functions. In M. Pivec & D. Dron (Eds.), *Handbook of research on serious games for educational applications* (pp. 269-287). IGI Global.
- Mathew, M. (2017, January 28). *Colors And Shapes Do Matter*. YourStory. <http://tinyurl.com/57cvbjwp>
- National Center for Education Statistics. (2019). *The Nation's Report Card: Reading 2019 (NCES 2020-459)*. U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences, National Center for Education Statistics. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/mkf5c7e2>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2019). *PISA 2018 results (Volume II): Where all students can succeed*.

Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/3pnd332v>

Padeliadu, et al. (2021). Developing Reading Fluency of Students With Reading Difficulties Through a Repeated Reading Intervention Program in a Transparent Orthography. *Learning Disabilities: A Contemporary Journal*, 19(1), 49-67. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1295344.pdf>

Saleh, M., & Althaqafi, A. (2022). The Effect of Using Educational Games as a Tool in Teaching English Vocabulary to Arab Young Children: A Quasi-Experimental Study in a Kindergarten School in Saudi Arabia. *SAGE Open*. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/mdr7rvb8>

Save the Children Philippines. (2021). Many Filipino children have limited access to books and other reading materials at home. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/36snvf5j>

Skinner, B. F. (1953). *Science and human behavior*. New York: Macmillan.

Tomas, et al. (2021). The Perceived Challenges in Reading of Learners: Basis for School Reading Programs. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 9, 107-122. doi: 10.4236/jss.2021.95009

Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.

World Bank. (2023, March 10). Learning poverty in the Philippines reaches new high of 90% due to pandemic, online classes. MANILA, Philippines News. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/yst9ynad>

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